

THE ENGLISH EFFECT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7865758>

Annotation: In this article, the study of foreign languages in a person's life the importance is discussed. Today, it is very important for everyone to know foreign languages. The fact that the world is becoming more and more globalized, and knowing two languages, is not just a fever, but a demand for time. Learning foreign languages is a life skill aimed at learning how to truly communicate and connect with others.

Keywords: foreign language, distance learning, social networks, modern technology, language specialist

The economic integration of European states, the redistribution of World Space, globalization encourage a person to perceive himself as a carrier of universal values, to think in global categories, to feel himself as a "citizen" of the world. He is no longer content with the circle of ethnic Microcosm, which leads him to seek ways to join the "distant world". One of the tools of such initiative is the study of a foreign language as a means of interethnic communication. The number of fluent speakers of one or more foreign languages in Russia is increasing every year – not only narrow specialists: translators, teachers, referents, but also those who use a foreign language in the context of everyday communication. Knowledge of a foreign language serves as a factor that activates the mechanism for changing the system of previously acquired vital meanings, values and directions of a person through his native language. The restructuring of consciousness is carried out, which causes many psychological problems for the subject of restructuring, including the problem of selfawareness, self-awareness, the formation of a worldview, including such a fundamental element as the picture of the world.

A group of linguists who base their assumptions about language on psychology argue that language is nothing more than "habit formation". They believe that language acquisition occurs through use, practice. They believe that "the more people use language, the better they learn it". The latest and most advanced discoveries and inventions in science and technology have been made at universities located in the United States of America, where English is a means of scientific speech. Almost all business negotiations are conducted in English. Knowledge of English is a great advantage internationally, whether you are on a

trip or a business trip, or you just talk to people from another country - you only need to know English. In addition many scientific literature is written in English. Therefore, knowing the language will help if you want to become the best specialist in your field of activity.

English in India

The historical context of India (which has been under British rule for over two centuries) has given Hindus easy access to master English and countless opportunities for development in science and technology. Many Hindus have become masters of the English language and have won many international awards in creative and comparative literature over the past few years.

Over the years, English has become one of the major assets in gaining global leadership for books written by Indian authors and films made by Indians in English. Famous Indian film director Shekhar Kapur's "Elizabeth" was nominated for several Academy Awards. No further evidence is needed to determine the advantages of the English language that it has brought to Indians internationally. English comes to the aid of the people of India and in trade operations around the world. English is the world's business management language, and knowledge of English has brought success to many Indian business managers.

English is becoming increasingly important not only for the medium of international trade, but also for interstate commerce and communication. People who travel from North to South for education or business in India mainly communicate in English, which has become lingua franca. In view of this, Parliament recognised English as an official language in addition to Hindi. Today, all the facts of history and change in India emphasize the continuing importance of learning English beyond the local languages.

World English.

So, today you have learned that knowledge of English is very important in today's world. You also saw a vivid example of how English affects the life of third world countries on the example of India. Modern English is a very diverse language, absorbing material from many other languages. It is spoken by more than 300 million native speakers and 400 to 800 million foreign users. It is the official language of Air Transport and cargo transportation; the leading language of science, technology, computers and commerce, as well as the main medium for education, publications and international negotiations. For this reason, scholars often refer to it as World English

The role of English as a global language.

It is estimated that around a billion people in the world use English as their native language or foreign language. The use of English as an official or semi-official language is common in more than 70 countries and plays a very important role in another 20 states. More than 1,400 million people live in English-speaking countries. About 75% of the world's mail and information is stored in English. Most of the approximately 50 million Internet users use English

In addition to the development of English as a world language, we will know some features that the world language should have. Regardless of its origin, it must be a practical and useful language that can meet everyone's needs. While English was originally English, there are now many varieties of it, including American, African, Indian, and Australian English. In addition, the English language now combines the dreams and aspirations of many peoples.

As well as experience from different countries. It is used to convey a huge amount of different information, whether it is the latest achievements in science and technology, enrichment of the experience of an ethnic group or business negotiations, in documenting cultural characteristics, in individual experience. His vocabulary was enriched with new words borrowed from other languages of the world. Over time, it is revealed that the global language changes beyond recognition as in English.

The big problem of Overcoming Love-Hate in relation to a foreign language has not yet been solved. In addition, there are strong comments about English by language communities such as French, Arabic, German and Dutch. Many nonlinguistic reasons also include nationalism, ethnicity, ideology, religion, politics, and culture when it comes to world language, often in combined and sometimes explosive mixtures.

Based on the previous rules, a questionnaire was compiled from yes / no questions that provide a place for clarification. 230 people volunteered to fill out the questionnaire.

To summarize, knowledge of English is for every industry representative new opportunities are the key. One door will open if you know your area well, another door will open if you also know the inlizz language. Exactly, knowledge of the language will open the door to the whole world.

From this study, it can be seen that in a rapidly developing global civilization, all children benefit from learning such an auxiliary international language as English at the same time as their native language. This allows them to easily communicate and interact with their peers around the world. As a result, this

strengthens the link between local and national languages in each country and a global connecting language such as English to maintain cultural diversity. The only way for all people on the planet to live peacefully lies through the adoption of a universal auxiliary language. And this issue should be considered immediately.

In any decision on the choice of the world language, the following should be taken into account:

- Opportunity to study it globally;
- His attitude towards the native language of each language group;
- Relationship between different native and national languages and the language of global communication within the same country;
- The issue of its use in world media;
- The need to collect and translate existing scientific and technical knowledge into the language of the chosen world, while constantly updating information from different areas of human activity;

This is the ability of the language to reflect the experience of different cultures and peoples without burdening its own “culture”. A Global language must follow simple grammatical rules, have as few exceptions as possible, and exclude letters whose pronunciation in words is impossible. In addition, it must be free from gender bias

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